

BioQuantum Record: Exploring otherness through extremophilic microorganisms

Anna Steward^{1,†}, Sebastian V. Gfellner^{2,†,*}, Carlo Pifferi³, Marie Catherine Sforza², Vincent Aucagne³, Matthieu Réfrégiers³

¹Academy of Fine Arts, Nuremberg, Germany

²UPR4301 Center for Molecular Biophysics (CBM), University of Orléans, Orléans, France

³UPR4301 Center for Molecular Biophysics (CBM), Orléans, France

† = The authors contributed equally to this work.

* = Corresponding author: sebastian.gfellner@cnrns-orleans.fr

ABSTRACT: The art-science collaboration BioQuantum Record aims to bridge scientific inquiry and artistic narrative using an astrobiological lens to explore fundamental questions regarding life, otherness, and the human perspective. We propose to move away from an anthropocentric view and send extremophilic archaea, "microbial astronauts", to potentially establish first contact with extra-terrestrial microorganisms. This parallels the search for life in astrobiology, which mainly focuses on the search for microbial life. This transdisciplinary approach merges art and science by maintaining a liminal state of uncertainty and openness to new forms of knowledge. We derived experimental methodological approaches from anthropological concepts to support a research stance in which the artist acts as a catalytic figure, enabling a transdisciplinary practice that unfolds collaboratively and opens new avenues for exploring anthropological concepts in art-science collaborations. This culminated in an art-science performance and exhibition that fused scientific protocols with artistic exploration to create science-fiction-inspired encounters. We conclude that astrobiology can be used as a means to explore otherness, with transdisciplinarity creating a shared space for encountering uncertainty and generating new inquiries.

Keywords: AstroBioArt, astrobiology, panspermia, sci-fi narrative, chirality, liminality

30 **Introduction**

31 *“The chances of this happening might be one in infinity. Put it this way: the chance*
32 *that there being intelligent alien life are, for me, infinitely higher than the chance there*
33 *being a creator god.”* —Comedian Tim Minchin when asked if he thought the
34 universe was full of life (Minchin 2009).

35 BioQuantum Record is the title of an evolving body of work emerging from an art-
36 science collaboration rooted in astrobiology. It encompasses the development of
37 exhibition and performance concepts, the presentation of the project in talks, and a
38 meta-level exploration of the nature of transdisciplinarity in relation to the concept of
39 otherness. The core principle of transdisciplinary work is seen as encounter: scientist
40 and artist meet in uncertainty. The artist engages with scientific material not as
41 subject matter but as a material, and the scientist approaches artistic inquiry not as
42 an illustration but as method, allowing space for the unknown to act. This paper
43 focuses on the transdisciplinary methodology emerging from art-science
44 collaboration.

45 BioQuantum Record revolves around a hypothetical new edition of the Golden
46 Record. Framed by this speculative sci-fi gesture, the project opens ontological and
47 epistemological inquiries central to astrobiology, such as how we define and perceive
48 life. Unlike the Golden Record sent aboard Voyager 1 and 2 to potentially contact
49 extra-terrestrial intelligence (NASA 2025), this transdisciplinary project proposes a
50 biological connection based on molecular chirality. The “handedness” of molecules
51 serves as both a poetic and scientific framework to explore how life might recognize
52 and interact with something fundamentally “other”. While life on Earth almost
53 exclusively uses left-handed (L -)amino acids and right-handed (D -)sugars as essential
54 building blocks, extra-terrestrial organisms might use molecules with reversed
55 chirality or a mixture of both elsewhere in the cosmos, forming a mirrored version of
56 life as we know it.

57 The project proposes sending an artistic vessel prototype hosting biochemical
58 materials and “a crew” of prokaryotes into space to initiate a chiral handshake with
59 their extra-terrestrial siblings. The crew candidates are extremophiles from the
60 Archaea domain, microorganisms that could potentially thrive in environments such
61 as Mars or other planetary bodies. The conception of the vessel draws on
62 panspermia theory (Kawaguchi 2019), the idea that life can travel between planets
63 on space debris, echoing life’s potential as a cosmic traveler, resilient, adaptive, and
64 capable of seeding worlds.

65 What happens when we send not only a message but life itself into the unknown?

66 *Post Voyager*

67 The BioQuantum Record is a post-Voyager concept that critically engages with the
68 implications of scientific progress and contemporary cultural-, societal-, and
69 philosophical thought, particularly the growing awareness of our pervasive
70 anthropocentric worldview alongside an emerging recognition of the interconnected
71 principle of life.

72 If we were to send another Golden Record into space today, what might the new
73 record look like? Based on the premise that microbial collectives may be the first
74 form of extra-terrestrial life that we will come into contact with, how might we
75 establish contact with them? Given the limitations of human sensory perception and
76 scale, how can we meaningfully engage with microorganisms, whether terrestrial or
77 extra-terrestrial? Despite technological advances, our understanding remains
78 fundamentally constrained by human experience.

79 Could we send microorganisms as intermediaries to make contact with their extra-
80 terrestrial kin? Although inevitably a gesture steeped in anthropocentric longing, the
81 narrative¹ framework playfully exposes the futility of transcending the limits of human
82 perspective. It becomes a narrative boomerang, which necessarily returns to us,
83 asking Michael Ende's question: "*What is mirrored in a mirror that is mirrored in a*
84 *mirror?*" (Ende 1984). Here, the paradox transforms into a potential opening: a koan.

85 *Microbial Astronauts*

86 Our astronomical candidates are the extremophilic archaeal species *Metallosphaera*
87 *sedula* and *Halobacterium salinarum*. *M. sedula* is a tough organism, growing
88 optimally in hot, acidic, metal-rich environments (Huber et al. 1989). It can be
89 cultured on meteorite breccia and Mars regolith (Milojevic et al. 2021), even when
90 adapting to heavy metals such as As, Cu, Zn, Cd, and Ni (Dopson et al. 2003), and is
91 able to survive desiccation (Kölbl et al. 2020). *H. salinarum* has evolved to live in
92 high-salinity environments (Eichler 2023), conditions that are not only found on Earth
93 but are also widespread throughout the solar system. Enceladus and Europa appear
94 to have salty oceans beneath their ice crusts (Lunine 2017), and Mars allows for the
95 formation of salt crystals (Pasteris et al. 2006; Davila et al. 2010), which can provide
96 shelter for potential microorganisms by serving as shields against harmful radiation
97 (Leuko et al. 2015).

¹ Here, "narrative" is used in the artist's sense as a reflective device rather than linear storytelling or plot. It may serve as an anchor point for the audience to enter the work, a lens to explore concepts, or a kaleidoscopic frame that fractures perception. In practice, the artist works with pre- and post-narrative structures, allowing for both framing and deconstruction of ideas.

99 Our proposal to enable contact between terrestrial microbial astronauts and
100 hypothetical extra-terrestrial microbial life is based on chirality. The term *chirality*
101 comes from the ancient Greek word χείρ (*cheir*), meaning "hand," as it refers to the
102 concept of "handedness." Chirality is a fundamental geometric property at the atomic
103 level that is extremely significant in chemistry and has important implications in life
104 sciences. Molecules with opposite chirality share the same atomic composition and
105 connectivity but cannot be perfectly overlaid in space, similar to the left and right
106 hand.

107 Instead of using both enantiomers, life on Earth has evolved using almost exclusively
108 L-amino acids and D-sugars (Barron 2008). This preference for one enantiomer over
109 another in living organisms is referred to as "biological homochirality", a phenomenon
110 that could serve as a potential signature for carbon-based life on other planets
111 (Glavin et al. 2020). Louis Pasteur wrote in 1874: "*The universe is asymmetric and I*
112 *am persuaded that life, as it is known to us, is a direct result of the asymmetry of the*
113 *universe or of its indirect consequences*". Inspired by this quote, and contrary to
114 Louis Pasteur, we can imagine that if the reason why life is asymmetric depends on
115 external bias factors, these can result in opposite outcomes if life were to emerge in
116 other places in the universe (Ozturk and Sasselov 2022). Under these premises, we
117 can imagine a carbon-based extra-terrestrial life that is a mirror version of life on
118 Earth.

119 Although enantiomers share the same chemical composition and atom connectivity,
120 they can behave very differently in biological systems; one enantiomer may be
121 curative, whereas the other may be ineffective or even harmful. The myth of Tantalus
122 from Greek mythology springs to mind: just as Tantalus was surrounded by food and
123 water, which he could never reach, we might encounter molecules that appear similar
124 but are fundamentally inaccessible or unhelpful to our life processes because of their
125 chirality. On a planet where life is a mirror version of our life, we could eat and still die
126 of hunger because our body simply could not utilize the molecules. The
127 "handedness" of molecules is not only a scientific concept but also a philosophical
128 framework that invites us to consider what happens when life recognizes and
129 interacts with something "fundamentally other": a possible mirror image of ourselves.

130 Stepping back from the poetic lens, it is with the rigors of science that a final point
131 deserves attention: while mirror-image biomolecules hold promising scientific and
132 therapeutic potential, the scientific community has recently undertaken a collective
133 effort to raise awareness of the risks associated with creating "mirror-image" life on
134 Earth (Adamala et al. 2024). BioQuantum Record plays with the concept of chirality,
135 imagining a metabolic chiral gift carried by the microbial extremophilic space
136 travelers within the vessel: L-glucose, the mirror form of glucose that terrestrial
137 organisms cannot metabolize, as an offering to their hypothetical extra-terrestrial
138 mirror-life kin.

139 *Art, Space, and Astrobiology*

140 The use of microorganisms as a medium in artistic practice has paved the way for
141 projects at the intersection of art and the life sciences. Early experiments, such as
142 those of Alexander Fleming, the father of penicillin, who created drawings using
143 different strains of bacteria (Dunn 2010), anticipated contemporary practice. Since
144 then, the use of microorganisms in art has gained increasing recognition, both as a
145 distinct artistic medium (Hauser 2020) and as a pedagogical tool for public science
146 communication (Yarzabal Rodríguez and Batista-García 2025). A prominent example
147 of biological art (BioArt) using microorganisms is Anna Dumitriu who fuses fine art,
148 performance and BioArt techniques in art and science collaborations (Fawcett and
149 Dumitriu 2018; Dumitriu 2024) including investigations of human-microbiome
150 relations (Greenhough et al. 2020). Meanwhile, Space Art has engaged with the
151 space environment for decades. An example is Inner Telescope by Eduardo Kac,
152 created with astronaut Thomas Pesquet aboard the International Space Station (Kac
153 2017). Despite these precedents, art explicitly addressing astrobiology remains rare.
154 Suzanne Anker’s installation “Astroculture (Shelf Life)” (Anker 2009-on going) is a
155 notable exception, cultivating plants under spectral lights and connecting this work to
156 NASA research on life-support systems.

157 BioQuantum Record builds on these precedents but approaches the intersection of
158 art and astrobiology from a distinct perspective: it merges a focus on microbial life
159 with extra-terrestrial motifs through extremophilic archaea, conceptualized as
160 microbial astronauts. Unlike previous projects that focused on plants or human
161 perception in space, the BioQuantum Record uniquely engages with extremophilic
162 archaea as active agents, inviting speculation on the possibilities of life beyond Earth
163 while merging artistic exploration and scientific investigation—and highlighting
164 encounters with forms radically different from our own. To the best of our knowledge,
165 no other project has worked with extremophilic archaea in a space-art context,
166 making this approach pioneering.

167 **Results and Discussion**

168 *Point Zero: Entering the Lab*

169 The artist arrives at the laboratory with ideas, sketches, and questions. Despite all
170 prior preparations, stepping into the lab means undergoing Ritual Zero²: a deliberate
171 un-knowing. Ritual Zero creates a space of open-ended inquiry, where the goal is not
172 to narrow a field but to expand a perspective. This methodological divergence
173 creates productive friction between the artist and the scientific partner, whose training
174 is to define variables, control conditions, and focus on specific, testable truths. The
175 artist's expansive "what if" meets the scientist's precise "how".

176 The artist begins as an intruder in the lab. They do not know the language and do not
177 belong; they require attention, which cuts into research time. Routine procedures are
178 disrupted. This causes irritation. But this irritation is not a flaw. It is the mechanism of
179 the practice. The artist, inhabiting the role of otherness, operates as a deliberate
180 agent of uncertainty. This position of liminality is an active, extended field that
181 interrupts habitual practice, evokes latent possibilities, and activates a fundamental
182 shift in perspective, inviting collaborators into a space where their certainties are
183 displaced.

184 Arnold van Gennep first introduced the concept of liminality in 1909 in his study of
185 rites of passage (Van Gennep et al. 2019). The term "liminal" comes from the Latin
186 word *limen*, meaning threshold or boundary. Van Gennep described liminality as the
187 middle phase in a three-part process: separation, liminality, and incorporation. In the
188 context of rituals, the liminal phase is the stage in which individuals have left their
189 previous status but have not yet assumed a new one; a state of ambiguity,
190 suspension, and openness. Victor Turner later expanded this idea, emphasizing
191 liminality as a period of profound potential, where structure and anti-structure coexist
192 (Turner and Abrahams 2017). In these "betwixt and between" states transformation
193 becomes possible. In the BioQuantum Record project, the liminal state is not only a
194 phase but also a method: a deliberate opening toward not knowing, allowing
195 encounters, and the emergence of new forms of knowing.

² The concept of Ritual Zero was derived from the methods that Sergey Kovalevich, a theatre director, student of Vladimir Klimenko (Klim), and art director of the International Theatre Resource Song of Songs, applied within the group. The artist was a member of this group, associated with the Jerzy Grotowski International Institute in Wroclaw, Poland, from 2006 to 2008. Ritual Zero was an integral part of both the methodology and training, functioning as an energetic practice of attunement.

196 *Immersion and Liminal Persona*

197 We propose immersion as a method for deliberately sustaining the liminal state. By
198 engaging in hands-on experiments, materials, and scientific practices without seeking
199 immediate mastery or closure, the artist remains in the space between certainty and
200 uncertainty. Immersion begins with attuning: observing how people move through
201 the lab, how scientific knowledge is organized, and how the space itself structures
202 attention.

203 At the heart of this approach is the collaborative work itself. Working alongside
204 scientific partners, not only to understand the theoretical framework but, crucially, to
205 engage in the tactile and material dimensions of the work. Handling protocols, tools,
206 and substances becomes a way of thinking through doing, in which insight emerges
207 from direct encounters rather than detached observations. Sensory involvement—
208 touch, texture, and proximity—acts as a portal for a different kind of knowing. This
209 mirrors the resonance described by anthropologist Lisa Messeri in her ethnography
210 of planetary scientists: a felt connection through which abstract concepts become
211 tangible via embodied, affective interactions with materials and processes (Messeri
212 2016).

213 Through sustained immersion, a new persona gradually takes shape: the lab shapes
214 the artist's liminal identity. This persona is twofold: it is both a mode for engagement
215 grounded in the quality of encounter and a trickster-like role, an agent whose
216 disruption opens space for alternative ways of thinking (Plant 2010).

217 *When Science meets Art*

218 The core principle of transdisciplinarity is humility: the willingness to recognize one's
219 ignorance against the backdrop of the other. Everything begins with finding and
220 establishing a common language; a certain word linked to a specific task may not
221 have the same meaning in art and science. The scientist, though guided by rational
222 boundaries, is invited to open their imagination within the collaboration (**Figure 1**).

223

224 **Figure 1. Artist and scientist meet in the laboratory.** Artist Anna Steward and scientist
225 Sebastian Gfellner together in front of a bioreactor of *M. sedula* culture grown on mineral
226 pyrite in the laboratory of the host institution.

227 Artists and scientists have different ways of conducting their work. The artist works
228 iteratively, with each cycle building on what emerged from the last—not toward a
229 fixed goal, but deeper into the questions the work itself raises. They own the right to
230 define when the work is completed. In contrast, scientists typically have no access to
231 experiments once they are initiated. Any changes during the experiment tend to
232 introduce errors. Therefore, it is crucial to carefully plan an experiment beforehand,
233 accounting for potential errors, because once it has started, scientists can no longer
234 intervene. Additionally, once an experiment is formalized in a scientific publication,
235 the peer review process leads to a never-ending “specimen” that could also be
236 proven wrong by future observations. The way of science is built upon continuous
237 improvement and discovery, imperfections that must be explained by others while
238 opening new gaps of knowledge: a never-ending story.

239 Where science is rooted in the empirical soil, artistic narratives can grow from it into
240 speculative air. The artist has the freedom to imaginatively reinterpret physical laws,
241 play with them, or inhabit frameworks that suspend them—all in the context of an
242 artwork. This is something a scientist, by the nature of their discipline, cannot and
243 would not aim to do. This divergence is complementary: where science seeks to
244 explain, art speculates, evokes, or reframes. Working within the context of artistic
245 imagination can enrich scientists' vision, potentially opening new research questions
246 that enhance scientific curiosity.

247 Art can serve as a vessel for the parts of a scientist's psyche that resist rational
248 frameworks, those impulses drawn to the beauty of the unknown or the enigma of
249 existence. It offers a medium through which scientists can momentarily detach from
250 logical paradigms and touch the parts of themselves that first fell in love with the
251 unknown, the part that method could never fully contain.

252 *From Art to Experiment: Stimulating the Scientific Process*

253 Among sugars, glucose ($C_6H_{12}O_6$) is one of the most crucial sources of energy for all
254 organisms on Earth, and exclusively the right-handed chiral form D -glucose is the
255 substrate for enzymatic reactions. Thus, we speculated that an extra-terrestrial form
256 of life could also use glucose as an energy source. However, what if they would use
257 the chiral mirror version L -glucose instead? Could we design an experiment to
258 determine whether Earth microorganisms can carry L -glucose as a chiral gift to their
259 potential extra-terrestrial kin? This hypothetical question stimulated scientific inquiry.
260 The materials and methods of the conducted experiment, as well as an in-depth
261 discussion of the experimental setup, can be found in the **Supplementary Materials**.

262 *Astrobiology and Anthropology as Transdisciplinary Allies*

263 Astrobiology is a relatively young discipline that has developed rapidly since the
264 advent of space exploration and the discovery of exoplanets (Cockell 2001). In 1975,
265 NASA launched the Viking program to search for signs of life on Mars, and in 1984,
266 the Search for Extra-Terrestrial Intelligence (SETI) Institute was founded.
267 Astrobiology explores the potential and origins of life in the universe, bridging scales
268 from the molecular realm of chemistry through the microscopic world of microbiology
269 to the macroscopic domain of planets and galaxies. In this sense, it resonates with
270 Feynman's spirit, connecting the extremely small with the extremely large
271 (Anniversary of a Myth 2009) and envisioning a new field of research. Astrobiology
272 also forces a confrontation with our deepest conceptual assumptions, unsettling
273 anthropocentric, terra-centric, and even life-centric assumptions, as we recognize
274 that what we seek may lie beyond our present imagination.

275 This movement between extremes and scale, perspective, and meaning creates a
276 liminal space in which categories dissolve and new connections emerge, echoing
277 patterns of anthropological inquiry, such as Victor Turner's notion of *communitas*
278 (Turner and Abrahams 2017), an intense experience of connection that arises in

279 liminal phases, temporarily dissolves hierarchy, and fosters collective bonds. While
280 Turner’s original focus was on human participants, subsequent posthuman
281 interpretations have expanded such concepts to include non-human agents,
282 materials, and processes, evoking a more-than-human field of shared becoming in
283 which diverse forms of knowing are entangled (Haraway 2016). Astrobiology, in its
284 own liminal search, echoes these patterns of entangled knowing, opening toward an
285 encounter with cosmic alterity.

286 We propose both anthropology and astrobiology as key allies in transdisciplinary
287 collaborations. Anthropology has the tools to examine how different domains
288 construct meaning and knowledge; more than a mode of observation, it enables a
289 situated, relational way of knowing, which is especially valuable when disciplinary
290 boundaries are in flux. It helps track how concepts shift between fields and how
291 language shapes perceptions. Rather than seeking synthesis or consensus, it
292 provides space for tension, ambiguity, and multiplicity. When brought into dialogue
293 with astrobiology, anthropology finds unexpected resonance. Both disciplines operate
294 in liminal epistemic zones, where categories are destabilized and understanding
295 must be renegotiated. Just as anthropology asks what it means to be human across
296 diverse life worlds, astrobiology asks what it might mean to be alive beyond Earth. In
297 this shared space of speculation and uncertain categories, anthropology reflects on
298 the assumptions embedded within each field, while astrobiology, stretching the
299 scope beyond human and terrestrial references, holds the possibility of an encounter
300 with otherness.

301 *From Ping-Pong to Pattern: Idea Emergence Between Systems*

302 The collaborative process itself became the generative ground for the artistic work,
303 as initial ideas for a vessel designed to make contact with potential extra-terrestrial
304 microbial life began to take shape. Co-author Marie Catherine Sfora remarked on
305 the toughness of *M. sedula*, sparking the image of extremophiles as astronauts—
306 survivors, travelers, and cosmic emissaries. Conversations with geologist Frances
307 Westall while exploring and examining the International Space Analogue Rockstore
308 (ISAR)³ collection further expanded the concept: the vessel gradually took on the
309 form of an asteroid, moving away from conventional engineering logic and inviting
310 alternative ways of thinking about spacefaring objects.

311 Building on this, a discussion with co-author Sebastian Gfellner introduced the idea
312 of the vessel as a generation ship—or “arkship”—carrying life across cosmic
313 distances. This progression—from envisioning resilient microorganisms as
314 astronauts, to the vessel echoing asteroid geology, to conceptualizing it as a
315 microbial arkship—traces the project’s collaborative evolution. This collaborative
316 progression marks the beginning of what we term the ping-pong phase. While
317 learning and doing intersect, the idea is shaped through quick exchanges, such as

³ <http://www.isar.cnrs-orleans.fr/isar/>

318 hitting a ball made of wet clay back and forth. This is the stage where the artist, while
319 still trying to understand the concept of chirality by making molecular models from
320 plasticine, is already following laboratory protocols to cultivate microorganisms. The
321 pendulum swings from the lab to the studio, from protocol to improvisation, from fact
322 to intuition. This dual movement between scientific inquiry and artistic speculation
323 shapes the emerging narrative gesture (**Figure 2**).

324
325 **Figure 2. From science to art.** Microorganisms grown on various mineral substrates
326 embedded in a space exposure well taken out of the scientific context become an artistic
327 object detached from its original purpose.

328 *Finding Analogies: Making Connections*

329 The artist follows lab procedures as far as possible. This deep engagement with both
330 physical substances and theoretical concepts is not about replication; it serves as a
331 method to evoke the emergence of ideas—moments when synapses connect
332 previously unrelated elements, placing them in experimental relation. Within this
333 methodical space, perceptual shifts occur. The act of counting cells under a
334 microscope becomes a moment of emergence: Is it a cell or a mineral fleck? The
335 rhythmic behaviors of magnetic stirrers each at their own frequency become music.
336 The line blurs. This moment of uncertainty, in which data and perception intertwine,
337 fuels an artistic process in which the red “Martian” soil from the host institute
338 basement merges with extremophile cultures and minerals, coalescing into a visual
339 essay. These moments of unexpected synthesis mark a shift from scientific
340 observation to artistic play. This is where freedom enters: when the artist stops
341 absorbing and begins transforming and creating meaning, and not simply mirroring it.

342 *Beyond Representation: Experimenting and Intervention*

343 At one point, co-author Carlo Pifferi said, “Ah, so you really want to do something, an
344 experiment? I thought this would be more of a representation”. This shift from
345 representation to intervention marks the point at which art and science begin to
346 actively shape one another, no longer running in parallel but becoming entangled.
347 The speculative narrative of extremophiles as interstellar travelers has become a
348 trigger for real scientific inquiry. This is no longer a mere exchange but a fusion: the
349 artist enters the scientific process to contribute, provoke, and open new pathways.
350 Questions arising from artistic inquiry can seed experiments that would otherwise not
351 occur. This is the unique role of the artist in science: to ask questions that no scientist
352 would ask, to propose impossible ideas that, through collaboration, become
353 experiments, objects, and new forms of knowledge (**Figure 3**).

354

355 **Figure 3. Exhibition “BioQuantum Record”.** Left: Tent installation of vessels displayed on
356 laboratory clamps. Right: 3D-printed ceramic vessel by Anna Steward. *Credits: Louise Cotte*
357 *and ESAD Orléans.*

358 *Exhibition and Performance*

359 The first series of vessels was presented in an immersive installation envisioned as a
360 deserted, possibly posthuman, laboratory tent. Suspended in the act of being filled
361 with mineral powders, biopolymer substrates, and microbial samples, sculptures
362 function as speculative objects—quasi-laboratory artifacts bridging scientific inquiry
363 and artistic imagination. The surrounding elements, including minerals, microbial
364 cultures, and reference materials, provided context, framing the installation as a
365 space for sensory encounters with speculative astrobiological questions. A glossary
366 offered an accessible scientific background, further supporting visitor engagement.
367 Building on this initial presentation, a second exhibition is being developed in which
368 chirality plays a central role, extending the project’s exploration of asymmetry and
369 mirrored forms in the context of life beyond Earth.

370 The exhibition opening was accompanied by the performance “Alien in the Closet”, a
371 collaborative work between researcher and artist (**Figure 4**). Lasting approximately
372 45 min and set to a live electronic score, the piece choreographs laboratory
373 techniques to narrate the story of microbial explorers from stasis to speculative
374 deployment across the cosmos. In the performance, scientist Sebastian Gfellner
375 enacted the improved extraction protocol developed during previous research
376 (Gfellner et al. 2025a), merging scientific precision with performative presence. Artist

377 Anna Steward prepared the chiral metabolic “gift” by pouring biopolymer infused with
378 minerals into Petri dishes, representing the L-glucose offering. In parallel, the
379 microbial astronauts were placed in cryogenic hibernation, poised for their voyage
380 aboard the arkship. The materials used included Mars-analog material and leftover
381 cell-mineral mixtures from the cell counts of an exposure experiment conducted in a
382 Mars simulation chamber (Gfellner et al. 2025b).

383 This reciprocal entry—the scientist into the artistic world and the artist into the
384 scientific world—is a foundational aspect of this work. It signifies not only a shift from
385 scientific protocol to a science-fiction narrative but also a profound methodological
386 fusion in which roles became interchangeable. Through this entanglement,
387 performance moves beyond conventional collaboration, proposing a new model for
388 transdisciplinary creation.

389

390 **Figure 4. Impressions from the performance “Alien in the Closet”.** Left: Artist Anna
391 Steward preparing a speculative arkship. Right: Scientist Sebastian Gfellner preparing the
392 microbial astronauts for takeoff.

393 **Conclusion**

394 Astrobiology is not primarily about extra-terrestrial life; it is about the nature of
395 otherness itself. This mirrors the authors' artistic practice of discovering strangeness
396 in the familiar, kinship in otherness, and familiarity with the weird. We propose that
397 this orientation toward otherness, whether cosmic, microbial, material, or symbolic, is
398 the underlying principle of transdisciplinary research. Transdisciplinarity is not simply
399 the merging of fields; it is the holding of a shared in-between space in which artists
400 and scientists encounter uncertainty and ambiguity. In this liminal zone—between the
401 empirical and the speculative, the methodical and the intuitive—new inquiries take
402 form. It is a field shaped as much by myth as by method, where knowledge is co-
403 created through encounters, relations, and transformations.

404 **Acknowledgments**

405 The BioQuantum Record project was developed during a residency hosted by the LE
406 STUDIUM Loire Valley Institute for Advanced Studies in Orléans, France. The two
407 collaborating institutions were the École Supérieure d'Art et de Design (ESAD) and
408 the CNRS Center for Molecular Biophysics (CBM) within the "Exobiology" and
409 "Synthetic Protein and Bioorthogonal Chemistry" teams. We also thank the Archaea
410 Center at the University of Regensburg, Germany, particularly Daniela Tarău for the
411 scanning electron microscopy images of *H. salinarum* and Robert Reichelt for his
412 valuable comments. Finally, we extend our gratitude to musician Noé Krizic for the
413 Alien in the Closet-live score. AI tools were used to assist with language and
414 phrasing; all ideas and content are the authors' own.

415 **Author Contributions**

416 A.S., S.V.G., and M.R. conceptualized the project. A.S., S.V.G., C.P., and V.A.
417 designed the experiments, and A.S., S.V.G., and M.C.S. cultivated the
418 microorganisms used in this study. A.S. designed and manufactured the artistic
419 objects and conducted the art exhibition. A.S. and S.V.G. designed and implemented
420 the art-science performance. A.S. and S.V.G. designed the manuscript. All authors
421 contributed to the editing and discussion of the manuscript.

422 **References**

- 423 Adamala, Katarzyna P., Deepa Agashe, Yasmine Belkaid, et al. 2024. 'Confronting Risks of
424 Mirror Life'. *Science* 386 (6728): 1351–53. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.ads9158>.
- 425 Anker, Suzanne. 2009. *Astroculture (Shelf Life)*.
426 <https://www.suzanneanker.com/artwork/astroculture-shelf-life>.
- 427 'Anniversary of a Myth'. 2009. *Nature Materials* 8 (10): 771–771.
428 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat2535>.

- 429 Barron, Laurence D. 2008. 'Chirality and Life'. *Space Science Reviews* 135 (1–4): 187–201.
430 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-007-9254-7>.
- 431 Cockell, Charles S. 2001. "Astrobiology" and the Ethics of New Science'. *Interdisciplinary*
432 *Science Reviews* 26 (2): 90–96. <https://doi.org/10.1179/isr.2001.26.2.90>.
- 433 Davila, Alfonso F., Luis Gago Duport, Riccardo Melchiorri, et al. 2010. 'Hygroscopic Salts and
434 the Potential for Life on Mars'. *Astrobiology* 10 (6): 617–28.
435 <https://doi.org/10.1089/ast.2009.0421>.
- 436 Dopson, Mark, Craig Baker-Austin, P. Ram Koppineedi, and Philip L. Bond. 2003. 'Growth in
437 Sulfidic Mineral Environments: Metal Resistance Mechanisms in Acidophilic Micro-
438 Organisms'. *Microbiology* 149 (8): 1959–70. <https://doi.org/10.1099/mic.0.26296-0>.
- 439 Dovey, Ceridwen. 2025. 'Imagining Exoplanets as Destinations: A Case Study of Artist-
440 Scientist Collaborations on NASA's Iconic Exoplanet Travel Bureau Posters'. *Journal of*
441 *Science Communication* 24 (4). <https://doi.org/10.22323/146020250722090112>.
- 442 Dumitriu, Anna. 2024. 'Algologies: An Artistic Exploration of the Entangled Relationship
443 between Seaweed, Women and Science through a BioArt Methodology'. *Applied*
444 *Phycology* 5 (1): 111–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26388081.2024.2397687>.
- 445 Dunn, Rob. 2010. 'Painting With Penicillin: Alexander Fleming's Germ Art'. *Smithsonian*
446 *Magazine*, July. <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/science-nature/painting-with-penicillin-alexander-flemings-germ-art-1761496/#zx3op7s8FrK2e14Z.99>.
- 448 Eichler, Jerry. 2023. 'Halobacterium Salinarum: Life with More than a Grain of Salt: This Article
449 Is Part of the Microbe Profiles Collection.' *Microbiology* 169 (4).
450 <https://doi.org/10.1099/mic.0.001327>.
- 451 Ende, Michael. 1984. *Der Spiegel im Spiegel: ein Labyrinth*. Edition Weitbrecht.
- 452 Fawcett, Nicola J., and Anna Dumitriu. 2018. 'Bacteria on Display—Can We, and Should We?
453 Artistically Exploring the Ethics of Public Engagement with Science in Microbiology'. *FEMS*
454 *Microbiology Letters* 365 (11). <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsle/fny101>.
- 455 Gfellner, Sebastian V., Cyril Colas, Guillaume Gabant, Janina Groninga, Martine Cadene, and
456 Tetyana Milojevic. 2025. 'Improved Protocol for Metabolite Extraction and Identification of
457 Respiratory Quinones in Extremophilic Archaea Grown on Mineral Materials'. *Frontiers in*
458 *Microbiology* 15 (January): 1473270. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2024.1473270>.
- 459 Gfellner, Sebastian V., Janina Groninga, Cyril Colas, et al. 2025. 'Assessing Cell Survival and
460 Biosignature Preservation of the Extremely Thermoacidophilic Archaeon *Acidianus*
461 *Manzaensis* after Exposure to Mars-like Conditions'. Preprint, December 31.
462 <https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2025-xc7vd-v4>.
- 463 Glavin, Daniel P., Aaron S. Burton, Jamie E. Elsil, José C. Aponte, and Jason P. Dworkin.
464 2020. 'The Search for Chiral Asymmetry as a Potential Biosignature in Our Solar System'.
465 *Chemical Reviews* 120 (11): 4660–89. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.9b00474>.
- 466 Greenhough, Beth, Cressida Jervis Read, Jamie Lorimer, et al. 2020. 'Setting the Agenda for
467 Social Science Research on the Human Microbiome'. *Palgrave Communications* 6 (1): 18.
468 <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-020-0388-5>.
- 469 Haraway, Donna J. 2016. *Staying with the Trouble: Making Kin in the Chthulucene*. Duke
470 University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv11cw25q>.

471 Hauser, Jens. 2020. 'Rehabilitating Bacteria: An Epistemological Art/Science Interface'.
472 *Shifting Interfaces: An Anthology of Presence, Empathy, and Agency in 21st-Century*
473 *Media Arts*, 193–210.

474 Huber, Gertrud, Carola Spinnler, Agata Gambacorta, and Karl O. Stetter. 1989.
475 '*Metallosphaera Sedula* Gen. and Sp. Nov. Represents a New Genus of Aerobic, Metal-
476 Mobilizing, Thermoacidophilic Archaeobacteria'. *Systematic and Applied Microbiology* 12 (1):
477 38–47. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0723-2020\(89\)80038-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0723-2020(89)80038-4).

478 Kac, Eduardo. 2017. *Inner Telescope*. https://ekac.org/inner_telescope.html.

479 Kawaguchi, Yuko. 2019. 'Panspermia Hypothesis: History of a Hypothesis and a Review of the
480 Past, Present, and Future Planned Missions to Test This Hypothesis'. In *Astrobiology*,
481 edited by Akihiko Yamagishi, Takeshi Kakegawa, and Tomohiro Usui. Springer Singapore.
482 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-3639-3_27.

483 Kölbl, Denise, Amir Blazevic, Mihaela Albu, Christoph Fasching, and Tetyana Milojevic. 2020.
484 'Desiccation of the Extreme Thermoacidophile *Metallosphaera Sedula* Grown on Terrestrial
485 and Extraterrestrial Materials'. *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Sciences* 7 (August): 41.
486 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspas.2020.00041>.

487 Kölbl, Denise, Marc Pignitter, Veronika Somoza, et al. 2017. 'Exploring Fingerprints of the
488 Extreme Thermoacidophile *Metallosphaera Sedula* Grown on Synthetic Martian Regolith
489 Materials as the Sole Energy Sources'. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 8 (October): 1918.
490 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.01918>.

491 Leuko, S., C. Domingos, A. Parpart, G. Reitz, and P. Rettberg. 2015. 'The Survival and
492 Resistance of *Halobacterium Salinarum* NRC-1, *Halococcus Hamelinensis*, and
493 *Halococcus Morrhuae* to Simulated Outer Space Solar Radiation'. *Astrobiology* 15 (11):
494 987–97. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ast.2015.1310>.

495 Lunine, Jonathan I. 2017. 'Ocean Worlds Exploration'. *Acta Astronautica* 131 (February): 123–
496 30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2016.11.017>.

497 Messeri, Lisa. 2016. *Placing Outer Space: An Earthly Ethnography of Other Worlds*. Duke
498 University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1215/9780822373919>.

499 Milojevic, Tetyana, Mihaela Albu, Denise Kölbl, Gerald Kothleitner, Robert Bruner, and
500 Matthew L. Morgan. 2021. 'Chemolithotrophy on the Noachian Martian Breccia NWA 7034
501 via Experimental Microbial Biotransformation'. *Communications Earth & Environment* 2 (1):
502 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-021-00105-x>.

503 Minchin, Tim, host. 2009. *The Skeptic Zone*. #26. April 17.
504 https://skepticzzone.libsyn.com/the_skeptic_zone_26_17_april_2009.

505 NASA. 2025. *Golden Record Overview - NASA Science*.
506 <https://science.nasa.gov/mission/voyager/voyager-golden-record-overview/>.

507 Ozturk, S. Furkan, and Dimitar D. Sasselov. 2022. 'On the Origins of Life's Homochirality:
508 Inducing Enantiomeric Excess with Spin-Polarized Electrons'. *Proceedings of the National*
509 *Academy of Sciences* 119 (28): e2204765119. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2204765119>.

510 Pasteris, Jill D., John J. Freeman, Brigitte Wopenka, Kai Qi, Qinggao Ma, and Karen L.
511 Wooley. 2006. 'With a Grain of Salt: What Halite Has to Offer to Discussions on the Origin
512 of Life'. *Astrobiology* 6 (4): 625–43. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ast.2006.6.625>.

513 Plant, John. 2010. *The Plains Indian Clowns, Their Contraries and Related Phenomena*.
514 Vienna, Austria. https://www.anjol.de/documents/100802_heyoka_neu.pdf.

- 515 Roberts, M. S., J. L. Garland, and A. L. Mills. 2004. 'Microbial Astronauts: Assembling
516 Microbial Communities for Advanced Life Support Systems'. *Microbial Ecology* 47 (2): 137–
517 49. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-003-1060-5>.
- 518 Turner, Victor, and Roger D. Abrahams. 2017. *The Ritual Process: Structure and Anti-
519 Structure*. 1st edn. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315134666>.
- 520 Van Gennep, Arnold, David I. Kertzer, Monika B. Vizedom, and Gabrielle L. Caffee. 2019. *The
521 Rites of Passage, Second Edition*. University of Chicago Press.
522 <https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226629520.001.0001>.
- 523 Yarzabal Rodríguez, Luis Andrés, and Ramón Alberto Batista-García. 2025. 'When Science
524 Meets Creativity: Elevating Microbiology Education With Art—Two Personal Experiences'.
525 *Microbial Biotechnology* 18 (3): e70099. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.70099>.